

Neutronics Simulation of a NuScale-Like SMR Core with the KANECS Code

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ABSTRACT

KANECS is a deterministic code that solves the multigroup neutron transport equation in three-dimensional Cartesian geometry, applying the Simplified Spherical Harmonics approximation (SP_N) in combination with the Continuous Galerkin Finite Element Method (CGFEM). In this work, KANECS is extended by replacing its original matrix-based storage formulation with a matrix-free approach. This optimization significantly reduces memory requirements while maintaining computational efficiency, allowing for high-fidelity simulations at both the assembly and pin-by-pin levels. In order to verify the improved KANECS framework, the simulation of a Small Modular Reactor (SMR), specifically a NuScale-like core, was performed. Given the characteristics of SMR (higher neutron leakage and a harder spectrum), the diffusion approximation is insufficient to capture their behavior accurately. Therefore, the KANECS model capability is well-suited for proper modeling. For verification, results are compared against reference solutions obtained from a Serpent Monte Carlo model developed in this work, enabling code-to-code verification at both assembly and pin-by-pin resolutions. Comparisons demonstrate that KANECS accurately reproduces the k_{eff} and power distribution for highly heterogeneous SMR configurations. The findings confirm that KANECS, enhanced with the matrix-free implementation strategy, makes it a reliable and efficient tool for advanced reactor analysis.

Keywords: KANECS, SP_N approximation, matrix-free, SMR, Serpent

1. INTRODUCTION

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) are becoming increasingly important as a key part of the next generation of nuclear reactors, due to their enhanced safety features and modular scalable design. It is worth noting that SMR cores exhibit a harder spectrum and higher neutron leakage due to their compactness. As a result, the neutronic core analysis requires advanced transport solvers instead of the classical neutron diffusion approximation with two energy groups, which is insufficient to adequately describe the high heterogeneity in both radial and axial directions.

Deterministic neutron transport methods still offer an attractive trade-off between accuracy and computational efficiency at lower-order approximations compared to the Monte Carlo method. Among these, the Simplified Spherical Harmonics (SP_N) formulation has emerged as a worthy option, providing a more accurate resolution than diffusion theory while maintaining reasonable computing time. Furthermore, combining with a Continuous Galerkin finite-element (CGFEM) spatial discretization permits the use of higher-degree polynomial basis functions, thereby improving the accuracy of flux-gradient representation in complex geometries.

Karlsruhe Neutronic Core Simulator (KANECS) [1] is a neutronic solver developed at the Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT). KANECS employs the SP_N and CGFEM approaches to approximate the steady-state 3D Cartesian multigroup neutron transport equation. The code was originally implemented using a matrix-based storage strategy with a Compressed Row Storage (CRS), which, while

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straightforward, imposes substantial memory requirements for large-scale, fine-mesh problems. This limitation becomes particularly significant when a pin-by-pin simulation is performed, where the number of degrees of freedom (DOF) can be extremely large and prohibited. In this work, KANECS has been extended to incorporate a matrix-free strategy [2, 3]. The improvement removes the need to store the large system by computing the operator action on-the-fly. Then, by precomputing shape function values and gradients and avoiding redundant evaluations, the computational cost of evaluating element integrals is significantly reduced. This optimization enables the reduction of memory usage and allows simulations with large DOF.

To verify the accuracy of KANECS, a SMR core model representative of the NuScale-like core design [4] was simulated. For the reference solutions, a corresponding Monte Carlo model was developed in Serpent [5] as part of the work. Additionally, a set of multigroup cross-sections was generated, enabling code-to-code comparisons. This work aims to demonstrate that the improved implementation in KANECS can accurately reproduce the k_{eff} and power distribution of the NuScale core, resulting from the higher refinement enabled by the matrix-free strategy. Results validated against Serpent at both assembly and pin-by-pin levels confirm KANECS as a reliable tool for advanced reactor analysis.

2. METHODOLOGY

The KANECS code is implemented on top of three main libraries: deal.II [6], PETSc [7], and SLEPc[8]. The deal.II finite-element library provides all the tools for solving partial differential equations (PDEs), including mesh generation, DOF management, and finite-element values. In the KANECS implementation, deal.II offers the polynomial basis function and numerical quadrature for the CGFEM; in addition, it computes the global indices and the elemental local matrix, which will be assembled into global operators and reordered using the Cuthill–McKee algorithm to reduce bandwidth. For solving the resulting large-scale operator, KANECS utilizes the PETSc library, which provides scalable vector and matrix data structures (including CRS and matrix-free formats) along with a broad set of PETSc’s Krylov subspace solvers, such as GMRES and BiCGStab. Additionally, preconditioning techniques, including Incomplete LU (ILU) and Incomplete Cholesky (ICC) factorizations, are applied to improve convergence rates. Finally, for steady-state criticality calculations, the neutron transport equation becomes an eigenvalue problem; therefore, SLEPc (used as an extension of PETSc) is employed to efficiently compute the dominant eigenvalue (k_{eff}) using methods such as the Power and Krylov–Schur solvers. Together, these libraries enable the solution of the steady-state multigroup SP_N neutron transport equations expressed in operator form in Equation (1), where $\hat{\mathbb{H}}$ is the transport operator, $\hat{\mathbb{F}}$ is the fission operator, and ϕ is the neutron flux.

$$\hat{\mathbb{H}}\phi = \frac{1}{k_{eff}}\hat{\mathbb{F}}\phi \quad (1)$$

2.1. Matrix-Free implementation strategy

The previous KANECS solver used a matrix-based assembly approach, in which the entire global system matrix is explicitly stored. This method is straightforward and efficient for low-order approximations. However, it can become prohibitively expensive for problems involving higher-order DOFs and vast amounts of cells, leading to significant memory demands. In contrast, the matrix-free strategy computes the action of the operator on-the-fly during each matrix-vector product, eliminating the need to store the full system matrix. This approach dramatically reduces memory requirements, enabling larger simulations. Nonetheless, matrix-free methods may require more Krylov iterations to converge than the matrix-based method, as the lack of an explicit preconditioner can lead to longer runtimes. So, to mitigate this, KANECS stores a block-diagonal matrix (the main block for each angular-energy group structure). The matrix is then assembled to construct an ILU preconditioner that preserves the dominant local coupling within each block. This provides a stronger approximation and improves the GMRES method, enhancing convergence speed without the cost of assembling the full matrix.

As matrix-free methods save memory, their performance is often limited by the cost of repeated quadrature evaluations. The deal.II library provides an optimized matrix-free kernel based on sum-factorization [3]. However, its design for the current transport formulation is not very friendly and flexible. For this reason, a custom matrix-free implementation was adopted, in which shape function values and gradients are pre-tabulated at quadrature points and reused during each operator application. This approach ensures full control over the operator evaluation, maintaining adaptability. The action of the transport operator is evaluated element-by-element without assembling the global matrix. Let \mathbf{x} be the input and \mathbf{y} the output DOF vectors. For each element K with quadrature points $\{\xi_q\}_{q=1}^{n_q}$, the DOFs are first projected to quadrature values using pre-calculated basis data presented in Equation (2), where the basis values $\phi_j(\xi_q)$ and $\nabla\phi_j(\xi_q)$ are pre-calculated once per element reinitialization, and ξ_q denotes the q -th quadrature point on the reference element.

$$u(\xi_q) = \sum_{j=1}^{ndof} \phi_j(\xi_q) \mathbf{x}_j, \quad \nabla u(\xi_q) = \sum_{j=1}^{ndof} \nabla\phi_j(\xi_q) \mathbf{x}_j \quad (2)$$

Later, the local physics are applied at each quadrature point, and the resulting contributions are accumulated into the output vector through back-projection to the DOFs shown in Equation (3), where Σ_q and D_q denote the removal cross-section and diffusion coefficient at quadrature point q , respectively, J_q is the Jacobian determinant of the mapping from the reference to the physical cell, and w_q is the quadrature weight.

$$\mathbf{y}_i = \sum_{q=1}^{n_q} [\nabla\phi_i(\xi_q) \cdot (D_q \nabla u(\xi_q)) + \phi_i(\xi_q) \Sigma_q u(\xi_q)] J_q w_q \quad (3)$$

This expression reproduces the action of the transport operator $\hat{\mathbb{H}}$ without explicitly assembling it. Efficiency is improved by reusing pre-tabulated basis data, which avoids redundant evaluations at every quadrature point. Compared to the matrix-full scheme, where each element requires $\mathcal{O}(4n_{\text{dof}}^2 n_q)$ operations to assemble, the present approach reduces the evaluation cost to $\mathcal{O}(8n_{\text{dof}} n_q)$, since basis functions and gradients are computed once per cell and then reused. It is worth noting that matrix-free evaluation cannot simply mimic matrix-full evaluation, as recomputing all quadrature contributions at every iteration would be prohibitively expensive. Instead, efficiency is achieved by minimizing redundant work through pre-tabulation.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, the numerical results obtained with KANECS using a matrix-free strategy are presented. This approach reduces memory demands, making it feasible to perform pin-by-pin simulations without encountering prohibitive storage restrictions. Leveraging this capability, a NuScale-like small modular reactor (SMR) core was modeled in Serpent as a reference case to validate code-to-code consistency at both the assembly and pin levels. The enhanced resolution enabled by fine mesh discretization and higher polynomial degrees translates into a substantial increase in the number of degrees of freedom (DOFs), which can now be handled efficiently within this framework. The results that follow demonstrate the applicability of the method for high-fidelity reactor simulations.

3.1. NuScale-like core description

The reference model is derived from the NuScale SMR concept. The benchmark considers the beginning of the cycle (BOC), neglecting fuel depletion and xenon/samarium effects. The core consists of 37 fresh UO_2 fuel assemblies with the typical 17×17 lattice and fuel rod pitch of 1.2598 cm. In total, there are seven different fuel assemblies with varying uranium enrichments, approximating an equilibrium

cycle. Additionally, for all the fuel assemblies, one contains fuel rods with gadolinium to control excess reactivity. A complete description of the geometry and material compositions is provided by [4]. A reference model was created using the Monte Carlo code Serpent 2.1.32 with the JEFF-3.1.1 nuclear data library. In contrast to the benchmark specification, our simplified model is a 2D configuration, which includes a full representation of the reflector, as the KANECS solver does not support void regions in the core map. This choice ensures consistency between the model codes. The core was modeled in the all-rods-out (ARO) state. The simulation was performed with 1,000,000 neutron histories per cycle, 5000 active cycles, and 500 inactive cycles, running on 32 OpenMP threads with a wall-time of approximately 16 hours. The calculated multiplication factor was $k_{eff} = 1.04165 \pm 1$ pcm. Finally, Figure 1 shows the Serpent model geometry, while Figure 2 presents the corresponding normalized assembly power distribution.

Figure 1. NuScale (ARO) Serpent model.

Figure 2. NuScale (ARO) Serpent normalized assembly power distribution.

3.2. Results Analysis

The KANECS model requires the generation of a consistent set of multi-group cross-sections; therefore, the classical two-step procedure was adopted in Serpent, yielding four-group cross-sections. The selection of four energy groups follows standard practice in SMR analysis, as it offers a robust balance between spectral resolution and computational efficiency. Two sets of homogenized cross-sections were derived. First, pin-level cross-sections were generated uniquely for each pin-cell type, and second, assembly-homogenized cross-sections were obtained by spatially homogenizing the fuel assembly lattice. This dual approach enables comparison at both the assembly and pin levels. All cross-sections were generated assuming isotropic scattering; therefore, a transport correction was applied to the total cross-sections to account for angular anisotropy effects. Both approaches were performed using the SP_3 approximation combined with a third-degree polynomial finite element method (p-FEM) to ensure accurate flux and gradient representation.

The KANECS simulations were executed using the GMRES solver with an ILU preconditioner, while the eigenvalue problem was treated with the Krylov–Schur eigensolver. Convergence tolerances were set to 10^{-6} for the neutron flux and 10^{-5} for k_{eff} . All computations were run on a workstation equipped with an AMD EPYC 7543 processor and 500 GB of RAM, using a single CPU core.

The results obtained for the analyzed configurations indicate that the effective multiplication factor is 1.04265 at the assembly level and 1.04278 at the pin-by-pin level, both showing excellent agreement with the reference value reported by Serpent. Figure 3 presents the normalized power distribution, where the assembly-level solution reproduces the same global distribution trend as in Serpent. At the same time, the pin-by-pin calculation provides a higher-resolution view of the local power profile. This finer detail enables the identification of the hottest fuel pin, a feature of particular relevance for safety analysis. Furthermore, Figure 4 compares the relative assembly power differences against Serpent, showing that in both approaches, the most significant deviations occur in assemblies containing gadolinium, due to the strong local absorption effects that are challenging to capture with high accuracy. At the assembly level, the errors are more evenly distributed across the core. In contrast, at the pin level, the central region remains highly accurate; however, larger discrepancies appear near the corners, likely due to heterogeneities such as gadolinium pins and neutron leakage effects.

A sensitivity analysis was conducted by varying the SP_N approximation order and the polynomial degree of the finite element method (p-FEM). A set of collective relative error metrics is defined in Equation (4), where A_i denotes the assembly power. These metrics include the deviation in k_{eff} , the maximum relative error, and the root-mean-square (RMS) relative error. The results of this sensitivity analysis are summarized in Table I. The results reveal that the highest discrepancies arise with low polynomial degrees in the finite element method (p-FEM). Increasing the degree significantly reduces errors, with a slight improvement from degree 2 to degree 3. In addition, the SP_3 approximation yields a more balanced estimate of k_{eff} compared to the diffusion model (SP_1), as is expected. Moreover, in the pin-by-pin analysis, maximum errors increase slightly compared to the assembly-level due to local heterogeneities. Thus, combining SP_3 with p-FEM at degree 2 offers a balanced accuracy, achieving a good trade-off between precision and computational cost.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \Delta k_{eff} &= 10^5 (k_{eff}^{KANECS} - k_{eff}^{ref}), \\
 \varepsilon_{MAX} &= \max \frac{|A_i^{KANECS} - A_i^{ref}|}{A_i^{ref}} \times 100, \\
 \varepsilon_{RMS} &= \sqrt{\frac{1}{37} \sum_{i=1}^{37} \left(\frac{A_i^{KANECS} - A_i^{ref}}{A_i^{ref}} \times 100 \right)^2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

(a) Assembly Level

(b) Pin-by-pin Level

Figure 3. NuScale (ARO) KANECS normalized power distribution.

 Table I. Results for different SP_N and p -FEM approximations at Assembly- and Pin-level.

SP_N	p -FEM	Assembly-Level			Pin-by-pin Level		
		Δk_{eff} [pcm]	RMS [%]	MAX [%]	Δk_{eff} [pcm]	RMS [%]	MAX [%]
1	1	-488	3.11	6.77	-194	2.82	7.75
	2	-152	1.28	2.54	-126	1.93	4.93
	3	-122	1.18	2.66	-126	1.92	4.91
3	1	-287	1.68	4.84	46	2.28	6.79
	2	63	1.12	2.95	113	1.38	3.14
	3	100	1.29	3.11	113	1.37	3.11

Figure 4. Relative assembly power difference with Serpent, Assembly Level (left) and Pin-by-pin Level (right).

Finally, Table II presents the performance metrics to compare the matrix-based and matrix-free approaches. It should be emphasized that both approaches yield the same numerical results. The analysis was carried out by varying the polynomial degree (p -FEM) while fixing the SP_3 approximation. The metrics include the time required for assembling the system T_{assembly} (in the matrix-free case, this corresponds to the preconditioner setup), the iterative solution time T_{solution} , and the RAM usage. The results show that at $p = 1$, the matrix-based approach is faster since the matrix-free method requires more iterations to converge, although the latter remains lighter in memory. However, as the polynomial degree increases, the matrix-based approach becomes increasingly demanding in computational resources and solution time, reaching the point of being prohibitive at $p = 3$ (especially at the pin level). In contrast, the matrix-free approach is not only considerably faster in the preconditioner setup but also the only feasible option at higher orders due to memory limitations, an important feature since higher-order discretizations are required to achieve good accuracy in simulations. Taking into account the previous sensitivity results together with the current results, this leads to the best trade-off configuration obtained with matrix-free at $p = 2$, which provides an optimal balance between setup time, solution time, and memory consumption.

Table II. Assembly- and Pin-by-pin SP_3 performance metric (matrix-based vs. matrix-free).

	p-FEM	Matrix-Based			Matrix-Free		
		T_{assembly}	T_{solution}	RAM	T_{assembly}	T_{solution}	RAM
Assembly	1	1.1 s	2.4 s	0.17 GB	0.11 s	10.41 s	0.09 GB
	2	28 s	51 s	1.4 GB	1.4 s	53 s	0.32 GB
	3	233 s	309 s	8 GB	14 s	187 s	1.4 GB
Pin-by-pin	1	22 s	108 s	1.7 GB	2 s	158 s	0.48 GB
	2	549 s	2917 s	23.6 GB	26 s	1525 s	4.3 GB
	3	5196 s	24199 s	182 GB	213 s	9846 s	22.6 GB

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this work, the KANECS code was enhanced with a matrix-free implementation strategy, enabling high-fidelity neutronic simulations of a NuScale-like SMR core at both assembly and pin levels. The results demonstrate good agreement with reference Serpent Monte Carlo solutions in terms of k_{eff} and assembly power distribution, validating the accuracy of the approach. Sensitivity analyses confirmed that the SP_3 approximation, combined with second-degree finite elements, provides the best compromise between accuracy and computational cost. Meanwhile, the matrix-free scheme significantly reduces memory consumption, making higher-order discretizations practically feasible. Overall, these findings establish KANECS as a reliable deterministic transport tool for advanced SMR analysis, offering the capability to perform detailed assembly and pin-by-pin studies that are essential for modern reactor design and safety assessments. Future developments will focus on extending the solver to time-dependent simulations, adding a cross-section module in NEMTAB format for coupling with a subchannel thermal-hydraulic code for multiphysics analysis, implementing parallel computing capability, and exploring matrix-free preconditioners to enable full 3D pin-by-pin calculations, where even block-diagonal storage may become prohibitive.

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